

Conformity Behaviour among Women of Punjab in Relation to their Social Freedom

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Abstract:- The present research was conducted on sample of 100 women from Jalandhar city of Punjab with the objective to find out the relationship of conformity behaviour with social freedom with respect to their locale (rural and urban) and level of Education (graduate and post graduate). The results of the study revealed that there exists a significant difference between rural and urban women in conformity behaviour and social freedom. Rural women of Punjab were found at higher edge in terms of conformity behaviour as well as social freedom. Whereas in case of difference between graduate and post graduate women in conformity behaviour and social freedom came insignificant. Similarly, no significant relationship was found between conformity behaviour and social freedom among women of Punjab.

Keywords:- Conformity Behaviour, Social Freedom.

I. INTRODUCTION

In India, women mostly live with their kids, husband and grandchildren. They are dependent on their son, daughter, and grandchildren. The women living in cities have better conditions than the women living in villages. Mostly in villages joint family system is followed. Older women are faced with many problems like uncomfortable relations with daughter in law and lack of interaction with grandkids etc. In the Indian constitution equal rights have been provided to all irrespective of gender but mostly women suffer because most of them are uneducated. Maximum women are housewife in India whose family does not allows them to work outside the house. They think that the women's job is only preparing the meal for their family and rearing kids. Even though the constitution has given free education from 6 to 14-year children. But in rural areas, few attend school because parents don't allow their daughters to go to school. Maximum parents think that they will get nothing in return from the education of their daughters. They think women should not get desirable jobs even though they are educated. Because of all this women are suffering from emotional and psychological and financial difficulties.

II. CONFORMITY BEHAVIOUR

Conformity involves changes in a person which are caused as a result of others' influence just in order to show obedience or to agree to people around them. In most of cases, conformity involves changes due to social influence. Society plays a vital role by influencing people through

modes of customs or rituals that are performed or followed by the majority of people of the society. In situation where accuracy is important, the rate of confirming the behavior of other people through information and social influence increases. People may conform because they wish to face the positive side of a group, to avoid being criticized and unobserved, to perform in a style with the intention of being perceived to be true or acceptable, and to stay away from feeling inferior to others.

The term conformity is often used to conform to the social role towards gaining the majority position in order to get liked or get fitted in a group or society by behaving normally as per the desires of the group or society.

There are two important types of conformity first is normative and second is informational but the reasons are numerous that why do people conform? In Normative conformity, changes in the behavior of a person take place to adjust well within the social order .whereas in Informational conformity due to lack of knowledge people follow the directions and use the information provided by the society or people around by following the customs and rituals of society. Compliance means shifting one's activities though still inside disagreeing. Internalization occurs in case a person changes his behavior because he wants to be like another person because others mandate that they should. Conformity is the change in thoughts or opinions of a person by the cause of social pressure to fit in society.

Most people conform in their group, friends, and peers. In group, people conform because they want to remain within group. Sis trunk and Mc David (1971) made the argument that women conformed more because of a methodological bias. Research has noted age differences in conformity. For example, as research was conducted on Australian children who showed that conformity changes with age i.e. conformity is inversely proportional to age. Children of age group 3 to 17 were considered under this study. Another study examined individuals that were ranged from ages 18 to 91. The results revealed a similar trend that older participants displayed less conformity when compared to younger participants.

It is observed that females conformed more than males. Similar viewpoints have been given by Reitan, et al (1964) in his study on Group membership, sex composition of the group, and conformity behavior. Females conformed more than males, and both males and females conformed more in

mixed-sex than in same-sex groups. Results were interpreted in terms of interpersonal relations between the sexes.

Behzad Anwar, et al(2013), conducted study on Women's Autonomy and their Role in Decision Making at Household Level: A Case of Rural Sialkot, Pakistan. The present study aims at understanding the impact of women's autonomy and their role in decision making at household level. In this study 138 married women were sampled from four villages of Tehsil Sambrial, Sialkot. The results showed a positive relation between women's autonomy and their role in decision making at household level. There should be balance of power between men and women. There is still a need to enhance women's autonomy and their role in decision making at household for the development in Pakistani society.

III. SOCIAL FREEDOM

As today's life is so expensive, it is really difficult for one person to run whole family. So middle class and lower-class families are also allowing their women and girls to work. Moreover girls are also allowed to work from the marriage point of view as the employed girl is preferred by middle class and lower middle class families.

Independence of India heralded the introduction of laws relating to women. Constitution has provided equality to men and women and has given special protection to women to realize their interests effectively. Special laws were framed to prevent indecent representation of women in the media and sexual harassment at workplaces. This law also gives women equal rights in the matter of adoption, maternity benefits, equal pay, good working conditions etc.

Empowerment of women, gender discrimination, and violence against women, have become serious subjects of sociological research in contemporary times, was hitherto neglected. While contemporary social changes have exposed women to unprotected socio-economic, cultural and political environment, there are no corresponding protective social systems and institutions of social justice to safeguard their interests.

Social freedom also influences decision making power of women as the same views have been supported by a study conducted by Muzamil (2014) . In this study 360 women from J&K (India) were selected. According to study the desire of women to get social freedom in society enhances the decision-making power of women which is beneficial for society. Whereas the decision-making power of males and family has a negative impact on the social freedom of women.

Shaigan Amin (2014) conducted study on social freedom among women belonging to Hindu and Sikh communities in Punjab with a random sample of 104 women from Patiala district of Punjab. The women social freedom scale by Bhusan (1987) was used which consists of 24 items. The data thus collected was subjected to 't' test. The study reveals no significant difference in social freedom among

women belonging to Hindu and Sikh communities and also in respect to rural areas whereas in context to urban areas the significant difference exists.

Singh (2013), conducted study on Challenges of Women Social Freedom In India: A Case Study of Women in Mathura and Agra City. The findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference between working and non-working unmarried women, between working unmarried and married women and also between non-working unmarried and married women with regard to their social freedom. However, there is a significant difference between working and non-working married women with regard to their social freedom.

Kang T.K. (2009) compared the attitude of male and female's towards women social freedom on sample of 140 respondents (70 male & 70 females) between the age of 25 to 35 years belonging to middle socio economic status and nuclear families. The minimum educational level of the respondents was graduate. Results showed significant difference in the attitude of male and females. The female were found to be more desirous of social freedom than males. whereas male were found to be reluctant to grant women their due social freedom. They preferred to see them as obedient daughter sisters and wives

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROBLEM

As it is well known that over the years status of women has not been up to the mark and their condition have been critical. Freedom was not given to women for studying and working outside. But in the contemporary world circumstances are changing and many steps have been taken to improve the condition of women as a result of which many women have acquired freedom to study and work outside their house. The current study imparted knowledge about the actual scenario of Social Freedom of women in Punjab. Apart from this study will also explored the information about how society behaves with woman in daily routine and how the woman's behavior or way of thinking affects her growth in the society. It provided basic understanding of the reasons behind in the growth of conformity behavior of the woman in the society.

The study will also gave information that how social freedom of the woman is being effected by conformity behavior and what are the different aspects which are needed to be explored to improve the conditions of the of society women. This study aims to explore the different aspect or ideas which will be helpful in framing new or improved policies for the society to take care such weaker aspects of the society especially women. Although the variable of Social Freedom has been explored previously also in relation to variables like nature of family, occupational encouragement, carrier aspirations and women empowerment and but it has not been explored in relation to conformity behavior among women that too in comparative nature. Keeping in mind the above mentioned points the researcher resolved to undertake the present study.

➤ Objectives

- To study conformity behavior and social freedom among women of Punjab.
- To find out the difference in conformity behavior among women of Punjab with respect to their locale and level of education.
- To find out the difference in social freedom among women of Punjab with respect to their locale and level of education.
- To explore the relationship between conformity behavior and social freedom among Women of Punjab.

➤ Hypotheses

- There exists no significant difference in conformity behavior between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab.
- There exists no significant difference in social freedom between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab.
- There exists no significant difference in conformity behavior between Graduate and Post Graduate Women of Punjab.
- There exists no significant difference in social freedom between Graduate and Post graduate Women of Punjab.
- There exists no significant relationship between conformity behavior and social freedom among Women of Punjab.

➤ Delimitations

- The study was delimited to 100 women (rural & urban) from Jalandhar city only.

➤ Method And Procedure

The present study aims at studying conformity behavior among women of Punjab in relation to their social freedom. Therefore, considering this a descriptive survey method was used in the present study. A descriptive study aims to investigate phenomena in their nature settings.

➤ Sample

In this current study, sample of 100 women was taken, out of which, data was collected from 50 rural & 50 urban areas. Further out of this 25 women were graduates and 25 were post-graduate. The data was collected from the Jalandhar city only through the application of a stratified random sampling technique. The stratified random sampling technique is generally used when the population is heterogeneous or dissimilar in nature.

➤ Tools

- Women Social Freedom Scale by Bushan L.I. (1987)
- Self-Constructed Questionnaire of Conformity Behavior.

V. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The present study was designed to assess Conformity behavior among women of Punjab in relation to their Social Freedom. After collecting the data from 100 women of Punjab, it was analyzed using t – test and co-efficient of correlation.

➤ Results pertaining to difference in Conformity Behavior between rural and urban women of Punjab.

Hypothesis 1 There exists no significant difference in Conformity Behavior between Rural and Urban women of Punjab.

Table 1 Showing Mean, SD and t – value of Conformity Behavior between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab.

Area	N	M	SD	t-value	Remark
Rural	50	36.82	7.26	3.69	Significant
Urban	50	31.36	7.49		

Fig 1 Mean and SD difference in Conformity Behaviour between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab

➤ Interpretation

It is evident from the above-mentioned table that the mean score for conformity behavior of rural and urban women of Punjab found out to be 36.82 and 31.36 respectively whereas standard deviation (SD) in case of rural and urban women came out to be 7.26 and 7.49 respectively. The calculated t – value for the conformity behavior of rural and urban women of Punjab came out as 3.69 whereas the table value is 1.98 at 0.05 and 2.36 at 0.01 levels of significance. As a calculated value is greater than the table value therefore the hypothesis i.e. there exists no significant difference in conformity behavior between rural and urban women of Punjab is not accepted.

Hence it can be said that there exists a significant difference in conformity behaviors between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab. It is quite evident from the table that social conformity has been found high in case of rural women. The researcher is of the view that such result came out because women in rural area lack in confidence and suffers from low self-concept. Because of lack of knowledge, low-level literacy, and less empowerment women in rural areas are more likely to conform in their daily life as compared to women in urban areas who are quite confident, educated, and empowered.

➤ *The results pertaining to difference in Social Freedom between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab*

Hypothesis 2 There exists no significant difference in Social Freedom between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab.

Table 2 Showing Mean, SD and t- Value of Social Freedom between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab.

Area	N	M	SD	t – Value	Remarks
Rural	50	15.34	5.37	3.19	Significant
Urban	50	11.82	5.62		

Fig. 2 Mean and SD difference in Social Freedom between Rural and Urban Women of Punjab

➤ *Interpretation*

The above-mentioned table shows that the mean score for the difference in Social freedom between rural and urban women of Punjab which came out to be 15.34 and 11.82 respectively whereas standard deviation (SD) in case of rural and urban women found to be 5.37 and 5.62 respectively. The calculated t-value for the Social Freedom between rural and urban women of Punjab came out as 3.19 whereas the table value is 1.98 and 2.63 at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance respectively. As the calculated value is greater than the table value, hence the hypothesis i.e. there exist no significant difference in Social freedom between rural and urban women of Punjab is not accepted. This shows that there is a significant difference in social freedom between rural and urban women of Punjab.

As it shows rural women are ranking high in social freedom as per the available statistics of the current research. The researcher is of the view that such result has come out because nowadays even in rural areas , women are provided freedom and people are more concerned about Women’s freedom with an aim of empowering women.

➤ *Results pertaining to difference in Conformity Behavior between Graduate and Post graduate Women of Punjab.*

Hypothesis 3 There is exists no significant difference in Conformity Behavior between Graduate and Post graduate Women of Punjab.

Table 3 Showing Mean ,SD and t – value of Conformity Behavior between Graduate and Post-Graduate Women of Punjab.

Level of Education	N	M	SD	t- Value	Remarks
Graduate	25	34.02	7.64	0.09	Insignificant
Post graduate	25	34.16	8.10		

Fig. 3 Mean and SD difference in Conformity Behaviour between Graduate and Post Graduate Women of Punjab.

➤ *Interpretation*

It is the evident from the above-mentioned table the mean score for conformity behavior among Graduate and Post graduate found out to be 34.02 and 34.16 respectively whereas standard deviation (SD) in case of rural and urban women came out to be 7.64 and 8.10 respectively. The calculated t – value for conformity behavior of undergraduate and post graduate came out as 0.09 whereas the tabulated value is 1.98 and 2.63 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance respectively. As the calculated value is smaller than table value, hence the hypothesis i.e. there exists no significant difference in conformity behavior between Graduate and Post Graduate women of Punjab is accepted.

This shows that there is no significant difference in Conformity behavior in women of Punjab as far as their level of education is concerned. The researcher is of the view that such results came out as in our society women are expected to conform in various situations. Although there is some improvement in the status of women but such improvement is prevalent at surface level only. Internally still women, irrespective of their levels of education conform in various situation in their daily life.

➤ *Result pertaining to difference in Social Freedom between Graduate and Post Graduate Women of Punjab.*

Hypothesis 4 There exists no significant difference in social freedom between Graduate and Post Graduate Women of Punjab.

Table 4 Showing Mean score, SD and t- value of Social Freedom between Graduate and Post-Graduate Women of Punjab.

Area	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Remarks
Graduate	25	13.16	6.08	0.73	Insignificant
Post Graduate	25	14	5.43		

Fig. 4 Mean and SD difference in Social Freedom between Graduate and Post Graduate Women of Punjab.

➤ Interpretation

It is evident from the above mentioned table that the mean score for Social Freedom of Graduate and post graduate women came out as 13.16 and 14 respectively whereas standard deviation (SD) for Graduate and Post graduate women came out to be 6.08 and 5.43 respectively. The calculated t – value for Social Freedom of Graduate and post graduate found out to be as 0.73 whereas the tabulated value is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 levels of significance respectively. As the calculated value is smaller than table value, hence the hypothesis i.e. there exists no significant difference in Social Freedom among graduate and post graduate is accepted.

This shows that there is no significant difference in Social Freedom in Graduate and post graduate women of Punjab.

➤ Result Pertaining to relationship between Conformity Behavior and Social Freedom among Women of Punjab.

Hypothesis 5 There exists no significant relationship between Conformity Behavior and Social Freedom among Women of Punjab.

Table-5 Showing Co- efficient of Correlation between Conformity Behavior and Social Freedom among Women of Punjab.

Variable	N	Coefficient of co relation	Remarks
Conformity behavior	100	0.59	Positive (average)
Social freedom			

➤ Interpretation

From the above mentioned table it is clearly evident that the ‘r’ value regarding Conformity Behavior and Social Freedom found to be 0.59. It shows that there lies average positive correlation between Conformity Behavior and Social Freedom among Women of Punjab. Whereas table value for the same at 98 df found out to be 0.198 and 0.265 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance respectively. Hence the hypothesis i.e. there exists no significant relationship between conformity behavior and social freedom among women of Punjab is accepted.

VI. CONCLUSION

On the basis of scores, results were obtained and following conclusions were drawn:

1. The hypothesis that there exists no significant difference in conformity behavior between rural and urban women of Punjab is not accepted. It is quite evident from the data that social conformity has been found high in case of rural women. The researcher is of the view that such result came out because women in rural area lacks in confidence and self-concept. Women in rural areas are more likely to conform in their daily life as compared to women in urban areas who are quite confident, educated and empowered.
2. The hypothesis that there exists no significant difference in Social freedom between rural and urban women of Punjab is not accepted. It shows that there exists a significant difference in Social freedom between rural and urban women of Punjab. Results show rural women are ranking high in social freedom as per the available statistics of the current research. It shows that nowadays even in rural areas women are provided freedom and people are more concerned about empowering women especially rural ones.
3. The hypothesis there exists no significant difference in Conformity behavior between graduate and postgraduate women of Punjab is accepted thus it can be concluded that there exists no significant difference between under graduate and post graduate women of Punjab with respect to conformity behaviour.
4. The hypothesis there exists no significant difference in Social freedom between graduate and post graduate women of Punjab is accepted thus it is concluded that there exists no significant difference in Social freedom between graduate and post graduate women of Punjab.
5. There lies average positive but statistically insignificant correlation between Conformity Behavior and Social Freedom among Women of Punjab.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As per the results, it has been found that there is significant difference in conformity behavior between rural and urban women. Women of rural areas have more conformity behavior than that of women of urban areas. It is the responsibility of family; society and nation to give the opportunity to women take their decision. Equal rights should be given to women. Another result indicates that post graduate women in social freedom scored high in comparison

to Graduate women. So women should be motivated as well as supported by Govt as well as society to pursue higher education so that they may enhance their skills and competence. Because education makes a person independent.

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